

Series: **PHYSICS**

Solomon I. Khmelnik

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>

Information transfer in biological systems by water and air

Annotation

It is shown that in molecules of water and air there can exist a bulk standing electromagnetic wave of high frequency. This wave can be modulated by the organs of the bioorganism. A wave modulated in this way can propagate through the water and air and affect the organs of another bioorganism. It is shown that such a wave propagates without energy loss. Based on this, it is shown that a highly organized structure comparable in reasonableness with the brain of an animal can exist in the air. Such a structure may be the collective brain of a community of bioorganisms.

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1. The electromagnetic volume standing wave.

It was shown in [1, 2] (as a consequence of solving Maxwell's equations) that an electromagnetic standing wave can exist in a limited volume of vacuum. This volume may have a variety of shapes. In a Cartesian coordinate system, the solution has the form

$$E_x(x, y, z, t) = e_x \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\beta y) \sin(\gamma z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (2)$$

$$E_y(x, y, z, t) = e_y \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\beta y) \sin(\gamma z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (3)$$

$$E_z(x, y, z, t) = e_z \sin(\alpha x) \sin(\beta y) \cos(\gamma z) \sin(\omega t), \quad (4)$$

$$H_x(x, y, z, t) = h_x \sin(\alpha x) \cos(\beta y) \cos(\gamma z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (5)$$

$$H_y(x, y, z, t) = h_y \cos(\alpha x) \sin(\beta y) \cos(\gamma z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (6)$$

$$H_z(x, y, z, t) = h_z \cos(\alpha x) \cos(\beta y) \sin(\gamma z) \cos(\omega t), \quad (7)$$

where E_r , E_ϕ , E_z are the electric intensities, H_r , H_ϕ , H_z are the magnetic intensities, $e_x, e_y, e_z, h_x, h_y, h_z$ are the constant amplitudes of the intensities, α, β, λ are the constants, ω is the frequency. These quantities are related by the following equations:

$$h_z = 0. \quad (8)$$

$$e_x = -e_z \frac{\gamma \alpha}{\alpha^2 + \beta^2}. \quad (9)$$

$$e_y = e_x \frac{\beta}{\alpha}, \quad (10)$$

$$h_y = e_x \frac{\varepsilon \omega}{\gamma}, \quad (11)$$

$$h_x = -e_y \frac{\varepsilon \omega}{\gamma}. \quad (12)$$

$$\gamma = \mu \omega, \quad (13)$$

$$\omega = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma^2 + \alpha^2 + \beta^2}{\varepsilon \mu}}. \quad (14)$$

Constants for cube

$$\alpha = \beta = \gamma. \quad (15)$$

The length of the half-edge of the cube is defined as

$$R = \frac{\pi}{\alpha}. \quad (16)$$

Then the formula for frequency in a vacuum takes the form

$$\omega = \frac{c\pi}{R} \sqrt{3}, \quad (17)$$

where $c \approx 3 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$ is the speed of light in vacuum.

A standing wave is not emitted through the faces of the cube and, in the absence of external energy flows, such a wave retains its energy, frequency and volume shape. This electromagnetic wave can be modulated at a lower frequency. In this case, this volume turns into a **keeper of energy and information**. In [2-4], well-known experiments and natural phenomena are considered, which serve as proof of the existence of such a keeper.

2. Electromagnetic standing wave in the molecules of water, nitrogen, and oxygen

A water molecule is a volume that stores a standing wave. In this case, the standing wave is stored in the space between the oxygen and hydrogen atoms, i.e. **in a vacuum** - see fig. 1.

Molecules of nitrogen and oxygen in the air are also the volume that stores a standing wave. In this case, the standing wave is stored in the space between the atoms of these molecules, i.e. in a vacuum.

Organic molecules are combined into organs in such a way that the relative position of these molecules remains unchanged. In this case, a **free vacuum space** with linear dimensions of about $3 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m remains between the molecules. A standing wave also appears in this stable volume.

Fig. 1.

Thus, it is possible to indicate stable volumes where a standing electromagnetic wave can be located. These options are listed in the table. 1. In a first approximation, we assume that these volumes have a cubic shape with the length of the half-edge R . This value is easily determined by the known linear sizes of the listed volumes - see table. 1.

Since the body standing electromagnetic wave in all these cases is in a vacuum, the frequency of this wave can be determined by the formula (17). The frequency f is related to this cyclic frequency ω by the relation

$$\omega = 2\pi f. \quad (20)$$

From (17, 20) we find

$$f = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} = \frac{c}{2R} \sqrt{3}. \quad (21)$$

We also determine the wavelength from (21):

$$\gamma = \frac{c}{f} = \frac{2R}{\sqrt{3}}. \quad (22)$$

Thus, the wavelength (22) and the half-edge of the cubic region of the existence of a standing wave are related by a relation of the form:

$$R \approx \frac{\gamma\sqrt{3}}{2}. \quad (23)$$

Table 1.

	Water	Nitrogen	Oxygen	Biological organ
	H_2O	N_2	O_2	
The distance between the molecules (m)	$3 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Molecule Size (m)	$3 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10^{-8}
Location of the standing wave region	Between oxygen and hydrogen atoms	Between nitrogen atoms	Between oxygen atoms	Between organic molecules
Atom radius ($pm=10^{-12}m$)	53 pm	56 pm	48 pm	
Interatomic distance $A=10^{-10}m$	0.9584 A	1.095 A	1.2074 A	
$R(m)$	$5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$6 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$
$\omega(s^{-1})$	10^{19}	10^{19}	$1.2 \cdot 10^{19}$	$5 \cdot 10^{16}$
$f(Hz)$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1.8 \cdot 10^{18}$	10^{16}
$\gamma(m)$	$2 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-8}$

3. Information transfer in water and air

We preliminary note the following. It is known that electromagnetic radiation interacts with molecules of a substance, causing radiation or absorption of electromagnetic radiation by molecules of a substance at certain frequencies [5]. Therefore, the molecules of a substance can interact through electromagnetic radiation. A multiple enhancement of the effect of such an interaction appears when the eigenfrequencies of the emitting and absorbing molecules coincide. Therefore, we can assume the existence in the body of generators of a certain frequency GF and receiver-analyzers of frequency AF.

At the same time, numerous works are known in which it is shown that all organs of animals and humans emit electromagnetic waves. These emissions are used in medical diagnostics.

The distance between the molecules of water and air is constantly changing. But the distance and volume between the molecules of organic matter in the body remain constant. This volume is usually filled with so-called **free water**, which is located in the intercellular spaces, vessels, vacuoles, organ cavities. Such water flows from the cells when they are dissected (and therefore called **free**). The volumes of the standing wave (with frequency ω_v) in water molecules are simultaneously in the intermolecular volume of the standing wave of organic matter (with frequency ω_o). For brevity, these waves will be called the ω_v –wave and the ω_o –wave. Since $\omega_o \ll \omega_v$, the ω_v –wave is modulated by the frequency of the ω_o –wave.

So, **free water molecules contain a modulated standing wave**, which we will call the ω_{vo} –wave. The frequency of the ω_o –wave depends on the type of surrounding organic molecules and on their state. This wave is polychromatic since the region of this wave is not cubic. The shape of this region affects the wave spectrum in the ω_{vo} –wave. However, the shape of this region depends on the type of organic molecules surrounding this region, and on the state of these molecules. It can also be assumed that there is a GF generator (mentioned above) in the generating organ. It can be used as a modulator of the ω_v –wave. Therefore, we can say that a water molecule with a ω_{vo} –wave carries information about the state of a particular organ. We will call such molecules **information molecules of water**, and the organ that generates such molecules will be called the **generating organ**.

One way or another, the generating organ forms the information molecules of water.

So, free water contains informational molecules. Free water serves to transfer substances from the environment to the cell and vice versa. Therefore, **free water** with information molecules is mixed with the **surrounding** water. Information frequencies are emitted by an information molecule because a water molecule can only retain its frequency ω_v . If an information molecule enters the surrounding water, then this radiation of the information molecule enters the neighboring **non-information** molecules of the surrounding water. The latter at the

same time become informational. In this way, information is distributed from the bio-organism through the surrounding water. Of course, part of the radiation does not find the receiver molecule and is lost in space. But the organ-transmitter works constantly and therefore it can be assumed that the concentration of information molecules is large in a large area surrounding the organ-transmitter.

Suppose that two organisms A and B live in the same aquatic environment. Suppose further that an informational molecule from a certain generating organ A (belonging to organism A) enters another organ B (belonging to organism B). Suppose that organ B has a frequency receiver-analyzer AF (mentioned above). Then the information radiation of this molecule can be recognized and organ B will carry out the corresponding reaction. Thus, organism B received information from organism A and reacted to this information.

So, in an aquatic environment, organisms can exchange information. In the same way, organisms can exchange information in the air. Indeed, from table 1 it follows that the nitrogen and oxygen molecules have similar characteristics with water molecules - the size of the molecule and the interatomic distance. Volumes filled with air can be on the surface of the body. For example, regular microroughness on the wings of beetles can create such volumes. The role of free water is played by "free air". Each peculiar shape of such volumes determines its frequency of the ω_o -wave. In this case, the beetle continuously generates a spectrum of ω_o -waves specific for this species. This transfer of information is used in the search for partners for procreation.

4. Bio-organism communities

So, bio-organisms located in an aqueous or air environment can exchange information over long distances **without the cost of energy to transmit information**. At the same time, there are no reasons prohibiting such an exchange of information between bio-organisms of various types, for example, from a predator to a person who can feel the approach of a predator. There are also no reasons prohibiting such an exchange of information between bio-organisms, one of which lives in water and the other in the air.

A special class is made up of such organisms that can exist only in the form of communities with the obligatory exchange of information without any tactile, visual, acoustic, olfactory contact. I immediately recall

ants and bees, but the person is probably also from this class of bioorganisms.

In [6], the behavior of the anthill is described and, based on the analysis of numerous observations and experiments, it is convincingly shown that the **anthill has a brain**. The role of neurons in this brain is performed by ants. A distributed brain exists, however, as the author notes, "many years of research on ants (and other collective insects) have not found any powerful information transfer systems." This question was asked in the first book on biological radiocommunication [7], where the author writes, "Only one causes a feeling of deep surprise. This is an insignificantly small power of the energy radiated by the brain during the act of transmitting feelings and experiences to a distance." We show that in our case there is an answer to these questions.

In technical systems, the power of the carrier frequency in a modulated wave decreases with distance. At the same time, the power of the modulating frequency decreases, i.e. this power is part of the carrier frequency power. It can be argued that while maintaining the power of the carrier frequency, regardless of the distance, the power of the modulating frequency is also preserved. We can say that in this case, the receiver is always next to the transmitter. However, in technical systems, it is impossible to ensure such proximity. In our case, the carrier frequency — the frequency of the ω_v –wave — is evenly distributed in space. The modulating frequency of the ω_o –wave “glides” along with the carrier frequency. Attenuation can only be caused by the fact that the carrier frequency is quantized in space. In this case, the ω_o –wave “glides” along the islands-molecules - carriers of the carrier frequency, attenuating in the voids between them. However, repeated repetition of the ω_o –wave with a time shift (and, therefore, phase) at the input of the receiver allows it to restore the signal with high accuracy. As observations on the same anthill or bugs looking for love show, communication efficiency persists for kilometers.

The foregoing is illustrated in fig. 2, where shown

1. ω_v –wave,
2. ω_o –wave,
3. modulated wave ω_{vo} –wave obtained if standing ω_o –waves would cover space without gaps,
4. modulated wave is a ω_{vo} –wave obtained when standing ω_o –waves are located in space with gaps.

Fig. 2.

A volume filled with water or air can be created by inanimate nature. Such a volume will also transmit information to the environment. Transmit aimlessly ... However, there may be organisms that need just such information to trigger some internal processes. I immediately recall the pyramids, amulets ...

5. Distributed brain

So, from the previous, it follows that there is a distributed brain of the anthill and the neurons of such a brain are ants. There are no reasons for the appearance of a distributed brain in any other community of bioorganisms. There are also no reasons limiting the mind of such a brain. Consider the features of the distributed brain (DB).

1. DB consists of many neuron-like elements, which we will hereinafter call independent and capable of activity neurons (ICAN)
2. The feature of the ICAN lies in the fact that they are physically autonomous and can operate to a certain extent, regardless of the DB.

3. IN are united by information communication channels and, thereby, create DB.
4. DB does not exist as a physical object.
5. In the process of its rational activity, the DB sends "leading" information signals (LIS) to individual IN. These signals determine the purpose of the independent actions of the ICAN.
6. It is important to note that the body sending the LIS is physically absent. One of the ICAN-1 under the action of LIS-1 sends LIS-2 to another ICAN-2.
7. The simplest ICANs do not realize their connection with the DB and their participation in the activities of the DB.
8. It must be assumed that DB can be compared by reasonableness with the brain of an animal.

There is no reason to believe that only social insects can be independent neurons in the DB. Animals can also be independent neurons. A distributed brain is present not only in a swarm of bees and anthill but also in a flock of birds, a school of fish, a herd of herbivores and a pack of predators. Without such an assumption, it is difficult to explain the coordinated movements of a school of fish or a huge flock of birds, which retains its shape not only during a purposeful flight but also in preparatory whirling. Recently, fireworks of hundreds of drones controlled from a single center were demonstrated in China. The consistency of whirling a flock of birds is comparable to the consistency of whirling of this "flock" of drones. So, there is a flock behavior in the absence of a "boss". Such behavior is often considered as a manifestation of some egregore. DB flocks is this **egregor**. The bird at the head of the flock is the very ICAN-1 which, under the action of LIS-1, sends LIS-2 to all other ICAN-2 - to all other birds of the flock.

A team of something united peoples (emotionally, informationally or organizationally connected) can also create a DB or an egregor. The existing idea of egregors is the idea of "*the collective unconscious reproduced by egregors as energy-informational complexes representing ... the forms of being of archetypes in psychology*" [8]. Simply put, this is something unconscious, existing in the form of an energy-information complex, the structure of which is out of the question. The author does not want to use this phrase to belittle the existing theory [8] - on the contrary, it strikes with a depth of analysis of the behavior of this collective unconscious and makes one doubt in the unconsciousness of egregors. The above is an attempt to come closer to

understanding the physical structure of egregor, as an energy-information complex.

Man-ICAN may also, like an ant, not be aware of his connection with DB. But some people sometimes feel this connection, not understanding where the information comes from and not completely understanding its meaning. Sometimes the same information comes to several people - then they say that "thoughts hovers in the air." Sometimes information comes (in a tense, emotional, unconscious request) in a dream (like Mendeleev). Apparently, it is in a dream that the human brain participates in the "socially useful" work of the DB.

Many prominent scientists have argued that consciousness exists outside the brain. So, John Eccles, the largest modern neurophysiologist and Nobel laureate in medicine, also believes that the psyche is not a function of the brain. Together with his colleague, neurosurgeon Wilder Penfield, who performed more than 10,000 brain operations, Eccles wrote the book "The Secret of Man". In it, the authors directly declare that they *"have no doubt that SOMETHING is located outside the limits of his body."* Professor Eccles writes: *"I can experimentally confirm that the work of consciousness cannot be explained by the functioning of the brain. Consciousness exists independently of it from without."* [9]

In view of the foregoing, it can be argued that consciousness exists in the form of DB. The more developed the consciousness of DB, the more developed the consciousness of each individual, and the more developed the consciousness of the individual, the more developed the consciousness of DB. Then it becomes obvious that for the existence of a developed universal human consciousness it is necessary,

- numerous humanity,
- consisting of smart individuals,
- united civilization,
- Earth with an air shell.

It follows, in particular, that

- education must be universal,
- the notorious golden billion will not last long (like Mowgli in the jungle),
- man in space is not capable of creative activity.

6. Conclusion

1. It is shown that in molecules of water and air there can exist a bulk standing electromagnetic wave of high frequency.

2. This wave can be modulated by the organs of the bio-organism.
3. A wave modulated in this way can propagate through the water and air and affect the organs of another bio-organism.
4. It is shown that such a wave propagates without energy loss.
5. Based on this, it is shown that a highly organized structure can exist in the air.
6. In such a structure, a separate bio-organism performs the functions of a neuron.
7. Such a structure may be the collective brain of a community of bio-organisms.

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